

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D2.4 – Interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality

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SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Executive summary

This document summarises and outlines the content of the interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality, which is publicly available here:

<https://up2030.notion.site/Toolkit-for-Stakeholder-Engagement-towards-Carbon-Neutrality-1b79a41fcb954cb5b5f457f3364c58e0>

This toolkit has been designed based on the methodology used for the UP2030 project, aiming to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging participatory urban planning and design. It is an interactive platform consisting of a simple checklist of the main stages of stakeholder engagement towards carbon neutrality, from planning to evaluation. Each item on the checklist can be expanded, presenting users with the tools and resources that can inform that particular step of the process.

The tools presented in the toolkit are those proposed and used by the partners of the UP2030 project during their own engagement activities and follow a unified structure to allow users of the interactive toolkit to implement them without further guidance. Each tool/method includes not only a general description and aim but also step-by-step guidance, a list of materials, resources and expertise needed, inclusivity points to consider, and use cases.

In order to make it collaborative and up-to-date, the toolkit itself allows users to suggest tools and/or methods that they would like to see included in the toolkit, along with contact information in case they require assistance or support when using the platform or the tools themselves.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages’ structure. Therefore, the content of this deliverable has been developed in alignment with TSPA, UIC, ICA, TUD and other partners from WP2, WP3 and WP4. The following table lists the deliverables (D) and milestones (MS) that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented. It is important to note that while this deliverable will be submitted during M8, it will continue to be updated as and when resources and input are available for future deliverables. Therefore, the list below includes input from deliverables not yet due.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D2.1 The 5UP approach and its contextualisation in the project cities</p> <p>D2.2, D2.3 UP2030 benchmarking report against state-of-the-art and identification of pilot opportunities</p> <p>D4.1, D4.2 UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities</p> <p>D4.3 Sustained engagement strategy of Learning & Action Alliances to promote the neutrality vision in the UP2030 pilots</p> <p>D6.6, D6.7 Neutrality Story Maps for the pilot cities</p>	<p>D2.5 Report on vision co-design methodology report and its application for pilot shared visions</p> <p>D5.2 UP2030 Service platform</p> <p>D5.5 Online Learning Programme materials</p> <p>D3.8, D3.9 Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice</p> <p>D5.4, D5.5 Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial intervention</p>
<p>MS02 Launch of UP2030 visual identification and virtual presence, and initial D&C plan</p> <p>MS05 Cities run first workshop on needs</p>	<p>MS06 Cities run second workshop on vision</p> <p>MS10 Cities run third workshop on action</p>

This deliverable is designed as a useable resource. It will support the engagement of each pilot city’s local stakeholder ecosystems to understand the needs, barriers and drivers for change, and to help co-create the visions and pathways needed to achieve such change. The process illustrated, along with the tools, will be deployed by the liaisons within the Learning Action Alliances (LAAs). Feedback on this deliverable will be sought and incorporated into further iterations of the toolkit to ensure its continuous usability. The ultimate target audience for this deliverable will be cities outside of the UP2030 partners who are working towards climate neutrality at a neighbourhood scale. The main beneficiary of the content is all the stakeholders who could affect or be affected by any interventions as they will be given the opportunity to contribute their ideas, knowledge and experience to ensure a just transition.

The toolkit will be used throughout the engagement process within the LAAs, with some methods having already been deployed in the early engagement phases, such as stakeholder mapping and fuzzy cognitive mapping. The tools within the deliverable will be available to be used throughout the whole project and beyond as engagement is an iterative ongoing process.

The interactive toolkit will, in the first instance, be hosted using the Notion platform and will be publicly available. It is foreseen that the toolkit could be moved to the Service Platform (**D5.2** UP2030 Service platform) once developed by M36 where it will remain and be promoted along with the other resources developed by UP2030. The toolkit will also be promoted through networks such as [NetZeroCities](#) and by the partners working in the fields of climate neutrality and resilience. In addition, the toolkit will be presented at conferences attended by UP2030 partners and via the partners social media networks.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
ICA	I-Catalist
LAA	Learning Action Alliance
MfC	Mapping for Change
MS	Milestone
RCities	Stichting Global Resilient Cities Network
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning & Architetur
TUD	Technische Universiteit Delft
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This document outlines the content of the interactive online toolkit and describes each section contained within it. The toolkit itself can be found at the following URL:

<https://up2030.notion.site/Toolkit-for-Stakeholder-Engagement-towards-Carbon-Neutrality-1b79a41fcb954cb5b5f457f3364c58e0>

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 - Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure.
- ❖ Section 2 – Background: summary of the objectives, target audience and limitations of the toolkit.
- ❖ Section 3 –Technical information about the toolkit: summary of the platform used for the development of the online toolkit, the reasons for choosing it and the back-end structure of the platform.
- ❖ Section 4 –Content of the interactive toolkit: description of the way the toolkit is structured, along with the contents of each page, sub-page and section.
- ❖ Section 5 –Sustainability plan: description of the long-term sustainability plans for the platform and its contents, to guarantee that they remain accessible throughout and after the project.
- ❖ Section 6 – Conclusions: final remarks about the expected use of the platform, its capabilities and limitations and its long-term sustainability.

2 Background

2.1 Objectives of the interactive toolkit

The objective of the interactive toolkit can be considered in two phases. Firstly, it has been developed to support the liaison partners and pilot cities in the UP2030 project to understand the needs, barriers and drivers to climate neutrality at a neighbourhood scale and co-develop a shared vision and pathway to achieving the vision. The toolkit is being used in conjunction with direct support from the Engagement Taskforce to ensure the project delivers exemplar use cases from the pilots. This first phase will collect feedback on the usability and relevance of the different tools as they are deployed in the pilots. Secondly, the toolkit will remain as a living public resource to be used by any other city seeking support with reaching their goal of climate neutrality. The toolkit will be updated and refined throughout the project lifetime to ultimately produce the most usable and useful output. The option for users to propose their own tools will help to serve as a way of keeping up with the state of the art in engagement methods as technology, knowledge and rhetoric changes.

2.2 Target audience

The process illustrated, along with the tools, will be deployed by the liaisons within the LAAs. The ultimate target audience for this deliverable will be cities outside of the UP2030 consortium who are, and will be, working towards climate neutrality at a neighbourhood scale. Most likely, these will be municipality departments or contracted consultants, therefore educated and literate but perhaps requiring extra support in stakeholder engagement methods. The development of this interactive resource connects to the notion that, for successful and sustainable change to be realized, it is essential to engage the stakeholders who could affect or be affected by any interventions and offer the opportunity to contribute their ideas, knowledge and experience to ensure a just transition.

2.3 Limitations

The main limitation of the toolkit is that it is currently only available in the English language and there is no resource allocated within UP2030 for translation.

The second limitation is that the majority of methods and tools have been deployed and tested in this context in the Global North, which means that some might require modifications to adapt them to a local context in the Global South.

The third limitation, although efforts have been made to minimise this, is that no toolkit could ever be fully comprehensive and account for every eventuality. The checklist structure allows for a large amount of content that is quickly accessible, therefore meaning more tools and methods can be included without the toolkit becoming unwieldy and unusable.

3 Technical information about the toolkit

The choice of Notion ([notion.so](https://www.notion.so)) as an online platform to host the interactive toolkit was based on the experience of MfC and TSPA who have used it extensively in other projects. It has proved to offer versatility, functionality and usability both for the UP2030 teams and the target users of the platform itself.

3.1 Platform used: Notion

Notion is a collaboration platform with modified markdown support that integrates kanban boards, tasks, wikis and databases. It is an all-in-one workspace for notetaking, knowledge and data management, project management and file management which does not require specialised training to use. It can be accessed by cross-platform apps and by most web browsers, without requiring a log-in to view and interact with pages made public by their creators[1].

Due to its versatility and ease-of-use, some partners (namely TSPA and MfC) were already using this platform internally to compile the methods used for the UP2030 project. Moreover, TSPA had proposed and created an “internal toolbox” in Notion to allow different partners to share the tools they were interested in implementing during the UP2030 project, divided into databases corresponding to the different stages of the stakeholder engagement process. In close collaboration and with TSPA, MfC built a public page within this structure to host the interactive engagement toolkit i.e., this deliverable. The page follows the structure described in Section 3.2.1 and includes guidance, information and interactive features to increase its usability for a public not familiar with the UP2030 project, along with detailed information about the project and the SUP approach.

3.2 Internal and public Notion pages

Within Notion, TSPA created a Project Management page for UP2030 – The UP2030 Toolbox – containing a series of databases grouping methods for the 4 main stages of stakeholder engagement: Analysis, Vision, Action and Upscaling (see Figure 1). The aim of this page was to collect and curate methods and tools proposed by different partners. It is, therefore, a page for internal use of the UP2030 consortium.

Figure 1: The four main stages of stakeholder engagement - Analysis, Vision, Action and Upscaling - with their respective activities

MfC created a similar page in Notion with the aim of making it a public repository of methods and tools, without giving visitors the options to edit the methods before validation from the UP2030 team. Since the aims of these two pages were complementary, a decision was made to combine them in such a way that all methods and tools added by the consortium into the Toolbox would be automatically added to the public repository.

3.2.1 Structure of the databases

There are four databases, one per stage of the Stakeholder Engagement process (see Figure 1). These have been combined into a master database to simplify the tasks of addition and revision of new tasks by partners. The database contains a set of pages – the “tool cards” – which follow a standardised template and a series of labels that allows users to easily identify:

1. The stage and activity in which a method is used (e.g., “Analysis – Needs Identification”)
2. The expected length or duration of the tool/method proposed
3. The format – online, in-person or both – in which the method can be implemented
4. The target audience for the method (e.g., decision-makers, NGOs, policymakers, youth)
5. The city or cities in which this method/tool has been used within the UP2030 project
6. The author of the method/tool (i.e., the partner or person submitting it to the Toolbox). It is important to note that some of the tools/methods submitted have been created by others, in which case the source material is referenced within the tool card.

An extra label called “status” - which determines whether a method is ready to be made available in the public toolkit – acts as a tag with two options: “draft” or “published”. This tag is hidden in the public view of the toolkit but simplifies the revision process by guaranteeing that only the tools that have been reviewed and are complete and exhaustive are available in the public toolkit.

Figure 2 below presents a screenshot of the top section of a tool card, showing the labels described above.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the top section of a tool card.

3.2.1.1 Structure of the tool cards

The template used for the creation of new tool cards contain a set of sections to be filled in by the person/partner submitting the tool:

1. Objectives: describes the general aims of the tool or method.
2. Results: A brief description of the expected outputs and outcomes of the tool.

3. Description: a general summary of the tool and its use.
4. Steps: a numbered list of steps to follow to implement this tool/method. Can include diagrams, supporting documentation and other resources to make sure that anyone reading the tool card can reproduce the method effectively.
5. Materials and resources needed: these can include resources like “working wi-fi connection” or materials such as “colour pencils and paper”
6. Expertise required for delivery/moderation: details if there is a specific need for expertise on, for example, the use of a platform or a methodology of analysis in order to organise and/or moderate the activities proposed.
7. Expertise required to participate: lists the required skills for participants, which may also be a limiting factor for the use of the tool in a specific context (e.g., a tool requiring use of digital platforms may be used only if the population is at ease with the use of digital technologies but should otherwise be avoided or require a modified setup).
8. Limitations: a list of the limitations of the method or tool proposed, such as time constraints, circumstances in which the method might not be useful or the need for several iterations. These might be related, but not fully overlap with, the materials and expertise required.
9. Inclusivity points to consider: tips to make sure that the method or tool is inclusive and non-discriminatory. This section aims to help users modify their intervention, if necessary, to adapt it to their specific circumstances and the needs of their target population.
10. References and use cases: when possible, partners should provide users with examples of the tool in use and/or source material to read more about its implementation.

Figure 3 below shows a screenshot of the content of a tool card as an example of how these sections are presented. The content was split in 2 columns in the screenshot to present it in this document.

<p>Objectives</p> <p>The aim is to help city leaders navigate the complex landscape of stakeholders involved in their projects, and build strong and productive relationships that can drive positive change.</p> <p>Description</p> <p>As explained by Stakeholder and Bourgois (2009), stakeholders can be defined as "actors who have an interest in the issue under consideration, who are affected by it, or who could have an active or passive influence on the decision-making and implementation processes". In practice, this implies actors that are affected by a problem at stake and/or have the capacity to change the course of action in a given territory. In these guidelines we provide a systematic (yet flexible) methodology to map key stakeholders and make an initial categorization of them. The guidelines do not cover the potential identification of relationships between stakeholders.</p> <p>Steps</p> <p>The recommended approach towards mapping and categorizing stakeholders is divided into three steps:</p> <p>1. Drafting an initial list of stakeholders</p> <p>One way of developing this list is by internally approaching contacts and then applying the snowball technique. This involves starting with a small group of stakeholders and then gradually expanding networks to include additional stakeholders as you identify them. To this end, the initially identified stakeholders are asked to suggest others who should be approached and invited to participate in the project, and then repeat the process with the new stakeholders who are identified (See below).</p> <p>Format of stakeholder mapping exercise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atomarily, a spreadsheet with pre-defined categories can help in the identification. <p>Inclusivity Points to Consider</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is important not to limit the mapping to those stakeholders that easily come to mind and one could easily see engaging in the co-creation process. On the contrary, the idea of starting off by identifying stakeholders is to make sure the process adapts to the stakeholders, and not the other way around. This means paying special attention to marginalised groups, people with disabilities, refugees and migrant communities, the elderly, etc. <p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several iterations of the process might be needed. The snowball technique might be time-consuming. <p>Expertise Required for Delivery/Moderation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> General knowledge of the population in the area of interest <p>Expertise Required to Participate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> None <p>References</p>	
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Figure 3: Screenshot of the content of a tool card, split in 2 columns.

3.2.2 Link between the internal toolbox and the public toolkit

The Notion pages were designed in such a way that the tool cards presented on the public “Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality” page are automatically retrieved from the internal “UP2030 Toolbox” page and sorted into categories that are more useful to the public. The publication of tool cards is dependent on them being tagged as “published” after reviewing. This ensures that the public toolkit is always up-to-date and reflects the latest changes made to the internal repository, while guaranteeing that only the tools that have been reviewed and are complete are published. It also minimises the effort required to synchronize both pages.

4 Content of the interactive toolkit

The interactive “Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality” is structured in the form of:

- A Home page containing general tips for stakeholder engagement and a simple checklist of steps to follow, each of which can be expanded to present the tools/methods proposed for that step.
- An Information page – called “About the UP2030 project” – which contains an overview of UP2030 and links to the UP2030 website. The aim of this page is to allow people to understand the context in which this toolkit was developed.
- A page for public contributions to the toolkit, called “Share your tools”, in which page visitors can submit – using an embedded form – the tools or methods they consider could be of interest to others visiting the Toolkit.
- A contact page – called “Contact us” – with information on how to contact the UP2030 team for questions related to the toolkit.
- A use policies page – called “Use of this toolkit – containing the moderation policy for content submission and a list of content restrictions. The aim of this page is to guarantee a good use of the platform and provide users with guidelines to detect and report misuse.

There is a menu bar at the top of each page that redirects users to all other pages, to simplify navigation. A footer on each page includes the logo of the European Union and a disclaimer about the source of funding for the UP2030 project.

4.1 Home page

The home page is the main page containing the Toolkit. It is titled “Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality” and it contains a short description of the toolkit itself, a section called “Before you begin your stakeholder engagement process” and the checklist of tools and methods. It also contains a call for contributions from the audience (which links to the “Share your tools” page) and a section called “Additional resources” containing all sub-pages.

The first section, called “Before you begin your stakeholder engagement process” contains links to three cards which are technically not tool cards but rather general recommendations on:

- How to effectively and inclusively communicate with stakeholders: contains a detailed list of considerations when it comes to designing a communication strategy.
- How to lower access barriers and guarantee an inclusive and diverse engagement process: presents specific tips for adapting engagement methods to different types of audiences – e.g., how to encourage attendance of people with caring responsibilities, of people with disabilities of physical impairments, of neurodivergent individuals, of migrant groups and/or individuals who face language or cultural barriers, etc.
- How to choose an engagement method according to the specific aims of the activity and to the target population: lists different types of engagement methods, along with the limitations and

benefits of each general category, with the aim of encouraging users to reflect in advance on the best strategy for engagement in their specific circumstances.

Figure 4 below presents a screenshot of the home page of the public toolkit as of 24 August 2023.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the homepage of the online Toolkit

4.1.1 Checklist structure and content

The central and main section of the homepage is a checklist of steps that one should follow sequentially to appropriately engage stakeholders towards carbon neutrality. To the left of each step there is an arrow that allows the step to be expanded, revealing the tools and methods related to that step. The instructions at the top of the page describe how to access them.

The items on the checklist are:

1. Identify your stakeholders
2. Lower barriers for engagement
3. Identify community needs
4. Identify barriers, assets and drivers for change
5. Co-create visions

It is important to note that the list will continue to be expanded as more tools are incorporated into the toolkit. The process – as presented in the public toolkit - currently ends at the co-creation of visions because all the tools submitted by partners so far (due to the current stage of the UP2030 project) fall into the categories of Analysis or Vision. However, as the project continues and more tools are available in the stages of Action and Upscaling (see Figure 1), corresponding steps will be added to the public toolkit. These steps have been so far excluded to avoid presenting empty items in the checklist and confusing users but are included in the information page as they are integral parts of the UP2030 engagement process.

The tool cards are automatically imported and sorted into these categories thanks to filters applied to the database described on section 3.2.1:

- A filter corresponding to the status (draft/published) defines whether each tool card is included in the public Toolkit.
- A filter corresponding to the stage sorts the cards into categories and places them under the corresponding title.

In order to avoid redundancy and improve usability, the tags that allow for this filter are hidden from the tool cards once these are made public.

4.2 ["About the UP2030 project" page](#)

This page contains general information about the UP2030 project's mission and methodology, along with a link to the UP2030 website (<https://up2030-he.eu/>). It also details the stages of the engagement process and the UP2030 planning cycle to make it easier for people to understand the different steps and stages in a visual way.

Figure 5 below presents a screenshot of the information page as of 24 August 2023.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the information page of the online Toolkit

4.3 “Share your tools!” page

This page presents a form that can be used by visitors to contribute to the toolkit by submitting tools or methods that they have used themselves and/or are familiar with and they consider appropriate for the scope of the toolkit.

It starts with a paragraph presenting general guidelines for submission - e.g., that images included must not be protected by copyright and that authorship must be attributed properly - and general information about the criteria by which the submissions will be evaluated.

After these general guidelines and information there’s a link to a form to submit tools, which opens in a new tab. The submissions of this form are collected in an internal Notion page that is currently hosted by Mapping for Change, as authors of the toolkit. This database of submissions will be transferred to the UP2030 Service Platform as soon as it is available. Each submission is to be reviewed by MfC and TSPA and, if approved for publication, the contents will be copied into the main database described in section 3.2.1.

A contact email address is requested in the form, which will be used not only to contact the authors in case of need for clarification or edit before approval of the submitted tool, but also to include it publicly in the tool card to allow other visitors to enquire about the specific tool if necessary (see below in section 4.4.).

Figure 6 below presents a screenshot of the contact page of the toolkit as of 24 August 2023.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the public contributions page of the online Toolkit

4.4 [“Contact us” page](#)

This page contains a short paragraph describing whom to contact:

1. For general enquiries or comments about the toolkit, or;
2. In case of specific questions about a tool or method.

For item number 2, a visual tutorial on how to find the email address of the author of each tool card is included, presenting detailed instructions and the advantages of contacting authors directly.

Figure 7 below presents a screenshot of the contact page of the toolkit as of 20 August 2023.

UP2030

Contact us

Quick links: [Home](#) | [About the UP2030 project](#) | [Contribute to this toolkit](#) | [Contact us](#)

Do you have a comment or a question? Please tell us all about it!

For general questions or comments
If you have general questions or comments about this toolkit, please feel free to email us at info@mappingforchange.org.uk.

Do you have a specific question about a tool/method?
If you have any questions or comments about one tool or method in this toolkit, you can contact the author of that tool directly by clicking on their name to find their email address (see tutorial below). While you can email info@mappingforchange.org.uk for all your questions, emailing the author will probably allow you to get your questions answered faster and more accurately. Please make sure you use the subject line "UP2030 Toolkit: [name of the tool (e.g. "UP2030 Toolkit: Define barriers, assets and drivers")].

UP2030 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOLKIT
STEP-BY-STEP: FINDING A CONTACT EMAIL

- 1. Select a toolcard**
Identify barriers, assets and drivers for change
Identifying barriers, assets...
Define barriers, assets & drivers
- 2. Click on the author's name**
Duration: 5-10 minutes
Format: Online / On-site
Target audience: Urban Planners / Citizens / NGOs / Youth / Local Stakeholders
City: Greater London
Author: Mapping for Change
- 3. Find their email address**
Mapping for Change
Contact: info@mappingforchange.org.uk
- 4. Use "UP2030 Toolkit" as your email subject!**

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Figure 7: Screenshot of the contact page of the online Toolkit

4.5 “Use of this toolkit” page

This page presents a short disclaimer explaining that the UP2030 consortium does not claim ownership over the tools presented in the toolkit and cannot take responsibility for misuse of the platform. This disclaimer is followed by a short section presenting the moderation policy and another one describing the content restrictions. At the bottom of the page, it provides users with guidelines on how to report any infringement of these policies.

5 Sustainability plan

The toolkit will be continuously updated throughout the UP2030 project. As such, the public toolkit page is not in its final form. However, through its integration with the internal project’s toolkit databases, used by all UP2030 partners, automatic updates will continue.

Since more tools will continue to be added, the way the tool cards are presented might change. In particular, cards with related or overlapping content (e.g. “Rapid Appraisal Participatory GIS” and “Participatory Mapping with Children) might be either combined or clustered under bigger thematic areas, in order to improve user experience and simplify navigation between similar tools. These changes can only be implemented once all (or at least, most) of the tools have been added by all partners.

5.1 Maintenance of the platform

The platform will be eventually hosted in the UP2030 Service Platform (D5.3), but until the platform is available it will remain hosted within a Notion account owned by MfC and will be maintained by TSPA and MfC.

Throughout the project, both TSPA and MfC will also remind all partners of the need for updating the tools for the internal and public toolkits and will be responsible for reviewing the submitted methods for publication. All partners are responsible for submitting tools and methods to the internal database.

5.2 Long-term sustainability

The toolkit will remain available in the Service Platform along with other outputs from the UP2030 project.

6 Conclusions

The public toolkit for stakeholder engagement towards carbon neutrality is a comprehensive and accessible resource designed to empower various groups and individuals interested in replicating the methodology and outcomes of the UP2030 project. By leveraging the valuable insights and experiences gathered throughout the UP2030 initiative, this toolkit aims to equip others with practical tools and guidance, enabling them to replicate the project's methodologies and achieve similar outcomes in their respective contexts, not only during the project's implementation but also long after its completion.

While this toolkit will be publicly available starting from 31 August 2023, its content and structure will continue to evolve as the UP2030 project continues. All partners of the UP2030 projects will continue to be trained on the use of the internal toolbox and the pilot cities and liaisons will be the first users of the public toolkit. This will provide valuable feedback on the applicability of the proposed tools and methods and the best way to present them in the toolkit.

The knowledge and experience gathered by the UP2030 consortium will continue to shape the way the toolkit is presented to external users, in order to optimise its usability and capabilities.

7 References

[1] Wikipedia, 2023. Notion (productivity software). [online] Available at: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Notion_\(productivity_software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Notion_(productivity_software)) [Accessed 20 July 2023]